

Egg-laying behavior of African white rice borer *Maliarpha separatella* Ragonot

A. Pollet, Entomology Laboratory, Gadjah Mada University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

We used a simple analysis of spatial distribution of egg masses to study the egg-laying behavior of *M. separatella*.

M. separatella is a very common stem borer (SB) of lowland rice in Africa. The insects rest on wild plants in ricefield borders during the day and fly into ricefields at night to mate or lay eggs. *M. separatella* has a limited flight range. Females have relatively high fecundity rate (500-600 eggs/female). They usually lay eggs in masses of 40-50 eggs each during an 8-10 d period.

Egg population was studied on variety IR5 during the 1985 wet season (WS) in central Côte d'Ivoire. We sampled a 30-m² ricefield (3 subplots of 10 × 1 m) every 3d day from 31 Apr to 3 Jun, when no new egg masses were found.

We tested for goodness of fit. Mean of studied data was 2-3 times greater than their variance (0.67 compared with 0.27); thus fitting the observed data to a Poisson distribution was impossible (see table). Using the method of Bliss and Fisher (1953), we fit data to the negative binomial law by computing the following intermediate parameters:

$k = 0.168$ (obtained using an iterative process based on maximum likelihood theory), and

$$p = \frac{m_x}{k} = \frac{0.27}{0.169} = 1.61$$

$$q = 1 + p = 2.61$$

$$R = \frac{p}{q} = \frac{1.61}{2.61} = 0.62$$

$$P_0 = \left(1 + \frac{m}{k}\right)^{-k} = (2.61)^{-0.169} = 0.851$$

$$n'_0 = P_0 \times n = 0.851 \times 330 = 280.91$$

Observed distributions of numbers of egg masses per m² of ricefield and expected frequencies computed for the negative binomial and Poisson distribution. Values and probabilities of their corresponding χ^2 and other statistics are shown. Central Côte d'Ivoire, 1985 WS.

Square meters × no. of egg masses	Medium A		
	Observed n	Negative binomial n'	Poisson n''
0	281	280.98	250.80
1	29	29.04	67.72
2	10	10.46	9.14
3	3	4.66	0.82
4	5	2.28	0.06
5	1	1.17	0.00
6	1	0.62	0.00
Sum	330	329.21	328.54
χ^2		3.9	120.87
P (χ^2)		0.691	<0.005
df		3	2
Mean	0.27		
Variance	0.65		
k	0.168		

Symbol	Sampling date
○	29 Apr
●	3 May
■	5 May
□	10 May
▲	13 May
△	17 May
▼	20 May
▽	24 May
◇	27 May
◆	31 May

○ Rice hills

Distribution of egg masses on rice mapped for half of the 30-m² field, based on observations every 3 d from 29 Apr to 3 Jun*. Central Côte d'Ivoire. 1985 WS.

*No egg masses were found on 3 Jun, so no data are shown.

from which results all expected frequencies n'_i (see table) using the next recurrent formula

$$n'_i = \frac{k+i-1}{i} \times R \times n'_{i-1}$$

where k , p , and q are parameters of the negative binomial $(q-p)^k$, m_x is the mean of data from the n unit samples ($n = 330 \text{ m}^2$), P_0 is probability of the first expected frequencies of n'_0 and n'_i and n'_{i-1} are any two successive expected frequencies with indices of $i-1$ and i .

Observed frequencies n_i were similar to the expected values n'_i that could have been obtained if all egg masses were distributed according to negative binomial distribution (see table). The corresponding χ^2 (3.9), gave too great a risk α (0.691) of being wrong when rejecting the null hypothesis.

The observed data must therefore be contagiously aggregated. Considering the holistic behavior of the insect, that they are not social insects, and that observed egg mass numbers are too small, such a grouping of data does not result from

females forming a group on a given night to lay eggs (see figure) and is not frequently done at random. It also could not result from accumulated eggs laid night after night in the same place by a few females.

Females can lay more than one egg mass a night, and all of these masses are located very close to one another. Different groups of egg masses resulted from the same number of individual females (see figure). Other experiments in different areas of Côte d'Ivoire supported these results. ■

Integrated pest management—other pests

Feeding behavior of parakeets on rice in Hill Region of Karnataka, India

A. K. Chakravarthy, K. Krishnappa, and N. E. Thyagaraj, Regional Research Station, Mudigere 577132, Karnataka, India

Roseringed parakeet *Psittacula krameri* Scopoli and blossom-headed parakeet *Psittacula cyanocephala* Linn. are the two main bird species that feed on rice in the Hill Region of Karnataka.

We studied damage done by parakeets to 4 ha of rice at Mudigere (13.0° 7' N and 75.0° 37' E) during Nov-Dec 1990. We used binoculars to observe the birds. We saw birds alighting on trees bordering ricefields at 0640 h. Most perched on tree branches or fence wires. At about 0720 h, three or four birds started to ricefeed in the fields. At about 0730, foraging groups of up to 20 birds of both species flew into the fields.

Individuals hovered by rice plants, cut, and then picked panicles. Each bird picked six to eight panicles during a period of 5-30 min, returned to its site, fed on the grains, and then flew back to the fields.

From 1000 to 1500 h, parakeets sought cover in trees adjacent to the ricefields. After 1500 h, five to six birds resumed feeding, which continued until

about 1745 h. Birds then returned to their roosting sites.

Foraging activity was interspersed by preening, beak cleaning, and resting. Individuals and groups spread over a wide area in a field but stayed within sight of each other. In 95% of the situations, the 55 flocks observed congregated only at field borders.

Foraging range of feeding flocks was 3-4 km and feeding range, 1.5-2.0 km. Flock size varied from 50 to 113 birds/ha ($n = 55$). Rice feeding lasted up to 24 d. Parakeets depredated stacked panicles soon after harvest. Birds preferred harvested panicles to panicles on the standing crop because they could feed conveniently on grains without hovering.

Panicle loss was computed as parakeets/ha $\times$ panicles/parakeet/day $\times$ feeding days. Panicle loss was converted to grain weight by counting and weighing all grains/panicle from a random sample of 100 panicles on eight different observation days.

Total yield loss was categorized as depredative loss (grain consumed) and extra-depredative loss (grain spilled). Mean depredatory loss of 71.4% differed significantly ($P = 0.05$) from the mean extra-depredative loss of 14.2% ($n = 8$).

Farmers lost 0.3 t/ha to parakeets. Considering that average harvest in Mudigere is 2.5 t/ha, yield loss caused by parakeets is economically important. Rice crops from milk grain stage to harvesting need to be protected from parakeets. ■

Effect of selected genera of plant parasitic nematodes on germination of rice seeds in eastern India

B. P. Hazarika, Indian Council for Agricultural Research Complex for Northeastern Hill Region, Manipur Centre, Imphal 795004, India

Rice in eastern India is seeded shortly after the premonsoon showers. In this situation, nematodes attack emerging seedlings and cause mortality.

We recorded seed germination in soils inoculated with nematodes to study their potentiality (Table 1). Results showed that only *H. mucronata* reduced seed viability significantly. We found that nematodes penetrated the seeds, affecting the embryos or inhibiting the emergence

Table 1. Effect of selected genera of plant parasitic nematodes on germination of Jaya seeds in eastern India.

Treatment	Germination (%)	Reduction (%)
Uninoculated	96.0	—
<i>Meloidogyne</i> (100 2d-stage juveniles)	94.5	1.5 (6.8) ^a
<i>Hoplolaimus</i> (100)	90.5	5.5 (12.9)
<i>Pratylenchus</i> (100)	90.0	6.0 (14.2)
<i>Hirschmanniella</i> (100)	81.5	14.5 (22.4)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate angular value = 15.3 at LSD (0.05).

of coleoptiles and plumules. Reduced viability due to nematode pathogens was due to mechanical injury and penetration of pathogens into root tissues, which caused rapid mortality in germinating